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Hydrogen reduction of bauxite residue pellets and effect of calcite addition

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Abstract

The utilization of bauxite residue (BR) was experimentally studied through hydrogen reduction, focusing on iron oxide reduction and the formation of leachable alumina phases. Three different types of pellets were made: one from bauxite residue, and the other two via calcite addition with varying calcite amounts. All pellets were isothermally reduced by H₂ gas in a thermogravimetry furnace at constant temperature under fixed hydrogen flow rate and reduction times. X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) coupled with Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS), were used for the phase and microstructural analysis. The hydrogen reduction rate is influenced by iron-bearing oxides formed during heating. Bauxite residue pellets exhibit a higher initial reduction rate than bauxite residue–calcite pellets as brownmillerite formation occurs in the latter one, which hinders iron oxide phase reducibility. The reduction kinetics are affected by the reduction temperature and calcite quantity added, while dominant phase formation during hydrogen reduction depends on their combined effect. There is no mayenite (Ca₁₂Al₁₄O₃₃) phase formation in reduced BR pellets, while with the addition of calcite, small amount of mayenite phase starts to appear during reduction, which increases with more calcite addition.

Key Words: Bauxite residue, hydrogen reduction, thermogravimetry, brownmillerite, mayenite.

1 Introduction

Bauxite is the main raw material for alumina production. Alumina is produced from the bauxite ore via hydrometallurgical process known as Bayer process, where bauxite ore is digested in caustic solution at high pressure to dissolve the alumina content. Almost all alumina producers around the globe uses the Bayer process for alumina production from bauxite ores ¹⁻⁴. However, an insoluble solid is separated during the Bayer process as a byproduct known as red mud or bauxite residue, BR (dewatered red mud). The commercial scale utilization of this residue is not easy due to its high pH, fine particle size, and high sodium oxide content. In 2015 it was reported that 4.5 billion tons of BR have been stockpiled worldwide ^{5,6}. However, BR contains many valuable minerals like iron, aluminum, titanium, calcium, sodium and rare earth elements (REEs), which will make it as a secondary raw material in future^{1,7,8}. Iron and alumina are the major constituents of BR, and their utilization has value and will decrease the residue volume largely. According to previous studies most of the iron recovery from BR were done by carbothermic reduction process⁸⁻¹⁰. During carbothermic reduction, large amounts of CO₂ emission are generated, which is a prime concern on perspectives of environmental regulation. Using hydrogen reductant as a substitute of carbon is more sustainable recovery process as it ensures no direct CO₂ during the reduction process, if hydrogen is produced using renewable energy.

Valorization of BR using hydrogen reduction has been proposed by HARARE EU project. The HARARE Project was started in 2021 and is a consortium of universities, research institutes and industrial companies from Norway, Greece, Germany and Belgium to recover metal production using ecofriendly means via BR valorization ¹¹. Some of the research has been done for the hydrogen reduction of BR^{2,12-14}. Pilla et al, ¹⁴ studied the low-temperature hydrogen reduction of BR- NaOH pellets for Fe₂O₃ conversion to Fe₃O₄ and the formation of sodium aluminate phase. The result showed that the conversion of Fe₂O₃ to Fe₃O₄ is high and around

96% when 20 wt.% NaOH added to BR for pelleting and then pellets were reduced with 5 vol.% H₂ in N₂ atmosphere for 120 min at 500 °C. In another study sintered BR-calcite pellets were hydrogen reduced, and these reduced pellets used for iron and alumina recovery. It was indicated that the alumina in the BR is converted to a calcium aluminate phase (mayenite), and further recovery of alumina in alkali leaching process by Na₂CO₃ solution was around 87%². Hydrogen reduction and magnetic separation of BR-calcite-lime self-hardened pellets has been studied by Ahmed et.al (2023)¹². It was found that the metallic iron percentage increased from 22 wt.% in the reduced pellets to 37 wt.% in magnetic fraction after magnetic separation. It was also emphasized that during the heating of the self-hardened pellets to the targeted temperature (1000 °C), the iron was present in two oxide phases of brownmillerite and hematite, originated from hematite in BR¹². Brownmillerite forms when hematite of the BR reacts with CaO of the added calcite and lime. As both brownmillerite and hematite have the different chemical compositions and the lattice structures, the rate of hydrogen reduction also varies as discussed previously¹⁵. In the BR-calcite pellets, during the hydrogen reduction Al₂O₃ in the BR forms mayenite as the major calcium aluminate phase¹⁶. Formation of mayenite is highly desirable as it has the highest leachability among other calcium aluminate phases in Na₂CO₃ leaching process^{17,18}. There are some studied related to the hydrogen reduction followed by smelting or direct hydrogen plasma smelting of the bauxite residue for iron recovery^{19,20}.

This study examines the hydrogen reduction kinetics of BR pellets and BR-calcite pellets, along with their phase evolution at varying reduction temperatures. Previous studies on the hydrogen reduction of bauxite residue-calcite pellets have primarily focused on systems with a stoichiometric ratio of bauxite residue to calcite¹⁶. In our previous studies^{2,16,21}, which maintained a CaO/Al₂O₃ ratio of 1 to promote the formation of 12CaO·7Al₂O₃, CaO·TiO₂,

and $2\text{CaO}\cdot\text{SiO}_2$. The effect of lower calcite percentages on phase formation and reduction behavior has not been extensively studied. However, in this work the $\text{CaO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ is below 0.5 is studied for further process optimization. This work aims to investigate the impact of reduced calcite content on the phase formation and reduction kinetics of bauxite residue-calcite pellets under varying temperatures. By examining the influence of lower calcite additions, this study seeks to enhance the understanding of phase evolution and optimize the reduction conditions for improved process efficiency.

2. Materials and methods

The overall experimental flow sheet of this work is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of experimental procedure and applied characterization methods

2.1 Materials and preparation

BR filter cakes and calcite were used as starting materials. The BR provided by Metlen Energy & Metals (formerly known as aluminum of Greece) and calcite from Omya S.A. Norway. These raw materials were dried in an oven overnight at 100 ± 5 °C. Then dried materials were deagglomerated and sieved below 500 μm . They were further mixed with varying calcite percentage in different ratios. Mixture 1 contains BR and 10 wt.% of calcite, and mixture 2 contains BR and 30 wt.% calcite. These materials were mixed in a lab size Erich mixture for homogenization about 30 minutes with 300 revolution per minute (rpm). After mixing, these materials were pelletized in a disc pelletizer via about 10 wt.% water addition. Three types of pellets were made as BR pellets (without calcite addition), BR+10 wt.% calcite pellets and BR+30 wt.% calcite Pellets. These green pellets were then dried overnight in an oven at 100 ± 5

°C. Hereafter BR pellets, BR+10% calcite pellets and BR+30% calcite pellets are named BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal, respectively.

2.2 Hydrogen reduction of pellets

The dried pellets were reduced in a thermogravimetry (TG) furnace for kinetic study of the hydrogen reduction. The schematic view and operational procedure of the TG furnace is presented here¹⁶.

The heating, cooling and reduction profiles were the same for all pellets. The pellets were heated in the presence of argon (Ar) to the targeted temperature with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and flow rate of 1NI/min. The calcite in the pellets was decomposed at temperatures 800 °C and 1000 °C, when the targeted reduction temperature reached, and therefore there was no remaining calcite (all converted to CaO) in the samples prior hydrogen introduction. This was confirmed by no mass loss observations upon reaching the target temperature. Hence, after getting stable weight, the hydrogen introduction was started. In case of 600 °C reduced pellets there may be weight loss due to calcite decomposition during reduction, as the decomposition of calcite is slow at this temperature. During the hydrogen reduction cycle, pellets were reduced in presence of H₂ gas for 90 minutes with a flow rate of 4 NI/min. Cooling was done by purging Ar (1NI/min) on the reduced pellets to avoid oxidation of the reduced metallic iron.

The calcination of the dried pellets (BR and BR+30cal) were carried out under argon atmosphere to investigate the phase transformation occurring during the heating. The pellets were heated to the targeted temperature with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and hold at the targeted temperature of 60 minutes and furnace cooled to room temperature. During the heating, holding and cooling cycle were carried out in presence of Ar purging with a flow rate of 1 NI/min.

2.3 Characterization of materials

The mineralogical phase analysis of the raw materials and reduced pellets were carried out using the X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique (Bruker D8 A25 DaVinci™, Karlsruhe, Germany) with the CuK α radiation and 2 θ diffraction angle range from 15 to 75° with step size 0.02°. A crystallographic database and EVA software were used for the diffraction analysis of the phases. For XRD analysis, these materials were powdered in a stainless-steel ring mill for 45 sec at a rpm 800. The microstructural analysis of the reduced pellets was carried out by a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Zeiss ultra 55LE, Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany), and the elemental analysis and mapping were carried out by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) (Bruker, AXS, microanalysis GmbH, Berlin, Germany). The raw materials elemental analysis was done using the X-ray fluorescence (XRF) technique (Thermo fisher, Degerfors laboratorium AB, Sweden).

In this work for thermodynamics calculation, each different pellets (BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal) reduction process was studied with varying temperatures. The actual amount of hydrogen purged during the whole reduction step was used for the thermodynamic equilibrium calculations. Oxides with weight percentages below 1 wt.% were excluded from these calculations and the masses of components were considered regarding the XRF data for the oxide pellets. The databases used included FTOxide, FactPS, and a developed database for mayenite at NTNU and Sintef. Equilibrium calculations were performed using the Equilibrium module in FactSage, while the free energy of the reaction was determined using the Reaction module with the FTOxide database. The mineralogical phase analysis of BR is presented later in the next section and indicated that iron is present in BR mostly in hematite and goethite phase. Aluminium is present in BR both in simple hydroxide (diaspore) and complex oxides (Cancrinite, katoite, and sodalite). Titanium is present in anatase, perovskite phase and calcium in calcite. These oxides are the major constituents of BR.

The chemical composition of the BR and calcite are presented in Table 1. A major fraction of the weight in BR is composed of iron oxide and alumina. Calcite consists mostly of CaO with minor fractions of SiO₂ and MgO.

Table 1: XRF elemental analysis of BR and calcite

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Phase changes during calcination

In the dried BR+10cal and BR+30cal pellets, iron major phase present in the form of hematite, calcium present in the form of calcite and alumina present in form diaspore, cancrinite and sodalite.

Calcination of BR+10cal pellets were done under argon at 600, 800 and 1000 °C and BR, BR+30cal at 1000 °C. The purpose of calcination is to identify the formation of iron-bearing oxide phases during the heating and before the reduction. With increasing temperature, the mass loss increases, mostly due to the more decomposition of calcite and alumina hydroxide. At 600 °C there was partial decomposition of calcite, while at 800 °C, 1000 °C the calcite decomposed completely. Figure 2 represents XRD analysis of BR+10cal pellets calcined at three different temperatures. This figure indicates that at lower calcination temperature of 600 °C some fraction of hematite converted to magnetite and at higher temperature of 1000 °C major conversion to magnetite and brownmillerite occurred. This phenomenon occurs due to the thermal decomposition of CaCO₃ into CaO and the formation of brownmillerite at higher temperatures, resulting from the diffusion and reaction of species such as CaO, Fe₂O₃, and Al₂O₃. At 800 °C, calcite decomposition occurs; however, complete reaction takes a longer

time. In contrast, at 600 °C, calcite does not fully decompose. These are clearly observed in the XRD spectra in Figure 2.

Figure 2: XRD spectra of calcined BR+10cal pellets at different temperatures.

Schematic in Figure A1 (in appendix) suggests a reaction path for the formation of $\text{Ca}_2(\text{Fe,Al})_2\text{O}_5$ and Fe_3O_4 during heating of the dried pellets to the targeted temperature. In case of BR pellets, the Fe_2O_3 is converted to Fe_3O_4 during heating and the remaining stays as Fe_2O_3 . The CO_2 is generated from calcite decomposition acts as a mild oxidizing and reducing agent when combined with the residual oxygen of the system which results partial reduction of hematite to magnetite. However, for the BR-calcite pellets iron stays in form of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ with Al in lattice, Fe_3O_4 and Fe_2O_3 . With increasing the fraction of calcite more $\text{Ca}_2(\text{Fe,Al})_2\text{O}_5$ phase formed during heating. There is no $\text{Ca}_2(\text{Fe,Al})_2\text{O}_5$ phase formation during the heating of BR pellets, and this may be due to the fact that the small amount of calcite present in the bauxite residue. TiO_2 in bauxite residue reacts with CaO to form perovskite (CaTiO_3) as the Gibbs free energy of formation (equation 1) is more negative than that for $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ (equation 2). The phase analysis of calcined BR and BR+30cal at 1000 °C are presented in the Figure A2 (in appendix). It is worth to note that, $\text{Ca}_2(\text{Fe,Al})_2\text{O}_5$ thermodynamic data was not available in any thermodynamic database, however, as aluminum content is minor in brownmillerite so $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ phase was used for the thermodynamic calculation.

3.2 Rate and extent of reduction

Figure 3(a) represents the weight loss and fraction reduced as a function of reduction time for BR, BR+10cal, and BR+30cal pellets at 1000 °C. Obviously, for all the pellets weight loss is insignificant after 30 minutes of reduction, which indicates that reduction is almost completed. The weight loss curves show that for all the three pellets there is an initial stage with higher rate of mass loss, which is followed by a significantly lower reduction rate. The initial rate of reduction (equation 4) was found to be very close for all the pellets. The total weight loss during reduction of BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal pellets are around 12.9wt.% ,11.9wt.% and 10.5wt.%, respectively at 1000 °C. BR reduced pellets have higher extent of weight loss due to higher amounts of iron oxide than the other pellets. This is because, with similar initial weight of three pellets, BR has a high percentage of iron oxide as compared to BR+10cal and BR+30cal pellets due to the addition of calcite and the subsequent dilution of iron oxides in the feed pellets.

The fraction reduced with respect to time for three different types of pellets at 1000 °C are presented in Figure 3(a). Fraction reduced was calculated as:

$$X = \frac{(\Delta w)}{(w_{in})} \quad (3)$$

Where, X is the fraction reduced, Δw is the actual weight loss during reduction (oxygen removed) for a given time, and w_{in} is the oxygen mass present in iron oxide at initial. The pellets primarily contain iron oxide, calcium oxide, alumina, silica, and titania as the major oxides. Among these, iron oxide is the only reducible oxide. Therefore, the observed weight loss during hydrogen reduction is solely due to the removal of oxygen from the iron oxide.

Figure 3: Weight reduction with time for 3 different types of pellets at 1000 °C (a) BR pellets reduction with variation of temperature (b) BR+10cal pellets reduction with variation of temperature (c) BR+30cal pellets with variation with temperature (d).

The initial rate of reduction is calculated as per the equation 4 shown below:

$$\text{Initial rate of reduction} = \left(\frac{Y(g)}{t(\text{min})} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ mol O}}{16 \text{ g O}} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ min}}{60 \text{ sec}} \right) = \left(\frac{Y}{t} \right) \left(\frac{1}{960} \right) \left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{sec}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where Y is the oxygen removed during initial stage of reduction, t is the time required for initial stage of reduction. By using equation 4 the initial rate of reduction of BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal were 9.2×10^{-4} mol/sec, 6.3×10^{-4} mol/sec and 6.1×10^{-4} mol/sec respectively. From the above results, it was found that the initial rate of reduction is faster for BR pellets as compared to BR-calcite pellets.

Majority of iron present in the initial dried BR pellets is in the form of Fe_2O_3 and their simplified reduction reaction with hydrogen can be described as follows (Data were collected from FactSage 8.1)

As shown in Figure 3(a), the initial reduction rate is above 85% for BR reduced pellets, however, for BR with calcite pellets it was lower and around (70-75) %. The rate of reduction in BR reduced pellets might be higher due to more amount of Fe_2O_3 to Fe reduction but in case of BR-calcite pellets the activity of iron oxide decreases due to the formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ during heating. This indicates that the reduction of iron from the $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ phase has a slower rate than the direct reduction of Fe_2O_3 . Based on experimental observations, the reduction process can be categorized under mixed control, transitioning between chemical reaction control and diffusion control, depending on the conditions. At constant temperature with increasing calcium content more $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ is formed and less Fe_2O_3 remained. The formation

of calcium ferrite slows down the reduction, likely because of lower chemical activity of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ than Fe_2O_3 to interact with H_2 gas. At higher calcite additions, the additional CaO does not necessarily lead to a proportional increase in brownmillerite formation. Instead, the formation of brownmillerite appears to be more strongly governed by temperature than by CaO content (Figure 2 and Figure A2), and the phase may also develop in localized regions that do not significantly hinder the reduction reaction. Furthermore, the microstructural features of the BR+10Cal and BR+30Cal pellets particularly porosity and the effective hydrogen diffusion pathways remain largely comparable. As a result, the small difference in their reduction rates is primarily dictated by the combined effects of phase formation and microstructure. At constant calcite percentage with increasing temperature, the reduction rate increases, indicating that the process is chemical reaction-controlled at lower temperatures and shifts towards diffusion control as the reaction progresses. Higher temperatures accelerate the reaction kinetics both due to faster endothermic chemical reactions and faster consumption of CaO product in simultaneous mayenite formation with brownmillerite reduction. As per thermodynamics calculation presented in equation 6 and 8, formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ and $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_7$ at 1000 °C and the formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ during heating is supported by high temperature sintering of BR calcite pellets from our previous work ²². Gibbs free energy of formation of gehlenite, mayenite and brownmillerite calculated by using Factsage 8.1 are presented below and from thermodynamics point of view the reactions occur.

3.3 Weight losses of during reduction

The weight reduction of BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal at different reduction temperatures are shown in Figure 3(b), Figure 3(c) and Figure 3(d) respectively. In BR pellets the initial weight loss is almost the same for 1000 °C and 800 °C, however, it is lower for 600 °C reduction temperature. This may be due to lower free energy of reduction of iron oxides to metallic iron at 1000 °C and 800 °C in similar partial pressure of $p_{(H_2/H_2O)}$ compared to 600 °C and also the diffusivity of hydrogen is higher with increasing temperature. In 1000 °C and 800 °C there are three reduction regimes with smaller transition and in 600 °C there are three reduction regimes with larger transition.

The reduction study of hematite by hydrogen from 600 °C to 1050 °C were carried out by Junguo and their coworker²³. They found that there are three reduction mechanisms during the reduction of hematite to metallic iron and higher activation energy during the conversion of wustite to metallic iron. Based on their experimental results, initially the reaction is chemically controlled at the reaction surface and transitioning to diffusion controlled toward the end of the process due to sintering. As compared to the present experimental work the rate of reduction is faster for iron oxide in BR pellets as compared to iron ore pellets which may be due to much smaller particle size of iron oxide in BR pellets.

The weight loss over time at different reduction temperatures for BR+10cal pellets is shown in Figure 3 (c). The weight losses are similar for 800 °C and 1000 °C, however, it is different for 600 °C. During heating of BR+10cal pellets to the targeted temperature some fraction of hematite reacts with CaO to form $Ca_2Fe_2O_5$ and the proceed of this reaction depends upon the targeted temperature shown in Figure 2. With increasing the heating temperature more $Ca_2Fe_2O_5$ forms, which is supported by thermodynamics data (ΔG increases from -57.36kJ to -63.71kJ from 600 °C to 1000 °C) and XRD (Figure 2). There are three iron complexes (hematite, magnetite and brownmillerite) in this pellet to be reduced. The reduction of brownmillerite is less favored at lower temperatures which may explain the slower reduction

at 600 °C compared to the 800 °C and 1000 °C. In addition, the reduction of Fe_3O_4 is accompanied with less oxygen removal than Fe_2O_3 with slow rate at 600 °C, and correspondingly less mass loss when it is reduced. Therefore, these may cause much slower reduction rate at 600 °C than the higher applied temperatures.

As the calcite fraction increasing the formation of brownmillerite is increases during the heating leading to less reduction rate for BR+30cal pellets. The weight loss curve exhibits a slower slope for the BR+30cal as compared to BR +10cal and BR pellets at all reducing temperatures.

The determined initial rates of reduction for the three pellets at different reduction temperatures are presented in the Table 2 as per equation 4. The results show that, the initial reduction rate is higher for BR pellets at three reduction temperatures, and it decreases with increase in calcite addition at specified reduction temperature.

Table 2: Initial rate of reduction (mol/sec) of pellets at different temperatures.

As the calcite percentage increases, more $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ forms, while less Fe_2O_3 remains during the heating of bauxite residue-calcite pellets at a constant temperature. This leads to a decrease in the reduction rate due to less reducibility of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ than Fe_2O_3 . However, the complete reduction behavior of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ and Fe_2O_3 , as well as its effect on the reduction rate, has been discussed in our previous work²⁴. The amount of calcite added directly affects the formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ (brownmillerite), a phase with lower reducibility than Fe_2O_3 . At lower temperatures (600 °C–800 °C), the reduction process is more strongly controlled by reaction kinetics, making the presence of brownmillerite more influential in slowing the reduction. Consequently, higher calcite additions promote greater brownmillerite formation during

heating, which decreases the reduction rate of pellets at these temperatures. This effect is more pronounced at lower temperatures than at 1000 °C, where the reduction is predominantly reaction-controlled.

3.4 The phases evolution during reduction

Figure 4 represents the XRD results for the phase analysis of BR, BR reduced, and BR-calcite reduced pellets at 1000 °C. Metallic iron (Fe), perovskite (CaTiO_3), gehlenite ($\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_7$), corundum (Al_2O_3), nepheline ($\text{Al}_4\text{Ca}_{0.03}\text{K}_{0.54}\text{Na}_{3.24}\text{O}_{16}\text{Si}_4$) and mayenite ($\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$) are the major phases of the reduced pellets. All iron oxides in the dry pellets were reduced to metallic iron in the presence of H_2 at 1000 °C for all pellets, which is supported by the XRD results (Figure 4). Aluminum was present in BR dry pellets as diaspore, and it converted to corundum phase after reduction. This is due to high temperature phase transformation of diaspore to corundum. There is no corundum phase present in BR+10cal reduced pellets at reduction temperature of 1000 °C. Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 present in dry pellets react with CaO at high temperatures to form $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_2\text{SiO}_7$ via reaction (6). After stoichiometric gehlenite forms with Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 that were present in sample, and remaining Al_2O_3 reacts with CaO to form mayenite via reaction (5), which is correlated to XRD results. There is no mayenite phase in the BR reduced pellets, however, mayenite phase formation increases with increasing calcite addition. The gibbs free energy of mayenite formation was not found in literature and thermodynamics tables, therefore a database developed for calcium-aluminate slags was used²⁵. Formation of mayenite is more favorable at pellets with higher calcite addition which may be due to the lower free energy of reaction (equation 6 and 7) and the limited amount of SiO_2 in the pellets. From our previous study it was observed that formation of mayenite is more favorable during hydrogen reduction as compared to gehlenite¹³.

Figure 4: XRD of reduced BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal pellets at 1000 °C.

The XRD of BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal at different reduction temperatures are shown in Figure A3,A4 and A5 (in appendix) respectively. In BR reduced pellets iron, perovskite, gehlenite, corundum, and magnetite are the major phases. At 1000 °C and 800 °C reduced temperatures, all iron oxide has been reduced to metallic iron.

In BR pellets, the major fraction of Al₂O₃ present in corundum and gehlenite phase at all the reduction temperatures. There is no mayenite phase in the BR pellets which may be due to the insufficient calcite present in the BR pellets for the formation of such phases.

The XRD of BR+10cal pellets at different reduction temperatures are shown in Figure A4 (in appendix). With increases in reduction temperature the metallic iron peak (2 theta =44.5°) is becoming more intense, which is due to the complete reduction of iron oxide complexes to metallic iron. At 600 °C reduction temperature, iron present in form of metallic iron, magnetite and brownmillerite. At 600 °C and 800 °C, major fraction of Al₂O₃ present in form of corundum and gehlenite however at 1000 °C a fraction of Al₂O₃ is converted to mayenite. Hence, the formation of mayenite is both temperature and concentration driven.

In BR+30cal pellets reduced at 600 °C and 800 °C, iron present in form of brownmillerite, magnetite and metallic iron as shown in Figure A5 (in appendix). Due to enough calcite present even at lower temperature may brownmillerite formed during the heating, however, at lower reduction temperature it was not reduced to metallic iron. With increases in reduction temperature metallic iron peak becoming more intense and at 1000 °C all iron complex reduced to metallic iron. Mayenite formation starts at 800 °C and 1000 °C. With increases in reduction

temperature the mayenite peak becoming more intense. As calcite increases, more CaO becomes available to interact with Al_2O_3 . With increasing CaO, under oxidizing conditions CaO reacts with Fe_2O_3 , and yielding brownmillerite. However, under hydrogen atmosphere the phase stability shifts and metallic Fe is formed and precipitated, leading to more CaO available to interact with gehlenite, yielding mayenite and calcium silicate. The presence of SiO_2 influences the formation of calcium silicate or calcium aluminium silicate phases during reduction. Additionally, sodium oxide (Na_2O) partially evaporates, while the remaining portion stays incorporated in the calcium aluminate phase ¹⁶.

3.5 Microstructural analysis

The microstructural image analysis for pellets was carried out, and results for BR reduced pellets and BR+30cal reduced pellets are shown in Figure 5. The phases marked in the Figure 5 were confirmed by using EDS point and area analysis. In BR reduced pellets, the metallic iron particles were distributed everywhere in the matrix and in some area iron particles are agglomerated as the reduction occurs at high temperature. Al in reduced BR pellets is present in corundum phase, which is shown in Figure 5(b). Other dominant phases found in BR reduced pellets was the same as BR+10cal and BR+30cal reduced pellets, except mayenite. The mayenite phase present in BR+10cal and BR+30cal reduced pellets has a higher amount in BR+30cal, which agrees with XRD results.

Figure 5: SEM images of (a) BR+30cal reduced pellets (b)BR reduced pellets.

The elemental mapping of BR reduced pellets and BR+30cal reduced pellets are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively. As seen, iron is present separately without overlapping with oxygen, signifying that iron oxide is fully reduced to metallic iron which agrees with XRD

results above. In BR reduced pellets, aluminium and oxygen are overlapping in some area, which indicates the existence of Al_2O_3 phase in the reduced sample. In some area calcium, titanium and oxygen are overlapped, this phase is perovskite which is shown in both Figure 6 and 7.

Figure 6: Elemental mapping of BR pellets reduced at 1000 °C.

In BR+30cal reduced sample, calcium, aluminium, and oxygen with minor fraction of sodium coexist in some area which manifested the existence of mayenite ($\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$) as shown in Figure 7. This phase is also found in XRD as well as EDS elemental analysis.

Figure 7: Elemental mapping of BR+30cal reduced 1000 °C pellets

The elemental mapping of reduced BR+30cal at 800 °C shown in Figure 8 (a) and elemental analysis different phase in 8 (b). As shown in Figure 8 (b), the white area is iron phase with iron content above 99.8 at. % and small amount of oxygen present, which attributed to metallic iron phase. The oxygen detected may be from the surrounding oxide phases as the iron particles are small. Elemental analysis of corundum and calcium aluminate phase are presented in Figure 13(b). Figures 9 (a) and 9 (b) show the elemental mapping and elemental analysis of reduced BR pellets at 600 °C, respectively. As shown from the EDS analysis Figure 9 (b), in some area iron combined with oxygen and aluminum and another area iron combined with oxygen and titanium which indicated that iron oxide complexes are not completely reduced.

Figure 8:(a) Elemental Mapping of Reduced BR+30% CaCO_3 pellets at 800 °C pellets.

Figure 8:(b) Compositional analysis of different phases in reduced BR+30% CaCO₃ pellets at 800 °C.

Figure 9:(a) Elemental Mapping of the reduced BR pellets at 600 °C.

Figure 9:(b) Compositional analysis of different phases in the reduced BR pellets at 600 °C.

3.6 Thermodynamics of hydrogen reduction of different pellets

For the thermodynamic analysis of the system and the simulation of the reactions, the chemical composition of the materials has been used in a simplified basis to reduce the degrees of complexity and computational time. Therefore, species having a composition of less than 1 wt.% have been excluded from the input species. Gas species and pure compounds have been selected from the FactPS database and oxide solutions from the FToxid database. Some of the solid solutions appeared in the calculations, are explained as follows: spinel is a cubic Al-Fe-(Ca)-O type of solid solution, nepheline is a NaAlSiO₄-KAlSiO₄ solid solution, that can dissolve excess SiO₂, Ca and Fe. Melilite is a solid solution with gehlenite (Ca₂Al₂SiO₇) and akermanite (Ca₂MgSi₂O₇) endmembers, Fe²⁺, Fe³⁺ can also be dissolved in the sublattices. Feldspar is a solid solution of Na-K-Ca-Si-Al-Fe-O with pure sparks of NaAlSi₃O₈, KAlSi₃O₈ and CaAl₂Si₂O₈. The mayenite phase is not including in the FToxid database and a private database has been earlier assessed and used also in the present study^{7,25}. The calculations for the reduction evolution and the phase assembly were implemented considering H₂ environment at the selected process temperatures.

Figure 10, presents the phase evolution when only BR is considered. At the low temperature regime, the predicted solid solution phases are nepheline, which is rich in NaAlSiO_4 and $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$, spinel phase which is mainly consist of FeAl_2O_4 , Fe in BCC structure, and several pure compounds such as $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$, CaTiO_3 , $\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}$, and CaSiTiO_5 . According to the experimental results, some Fe_3O_4 remained after the course of reduction, however, according to the thermodynamics the Spinel phase is stable. However, the XRD peak indicate some broadening which might forecast a solid solution, something that however requires more analytical work. This is due to the thermodynamic stability of the spinel phase in such conditions, which experimentally might not be observable due to kinetic constraints.

Figure 10: Thermodynamices calculation of BR pellets at different reduction temperature

At the intermediate temperature of 800 °C the stable solution phases are Fe-BCC, melilite rich in $\text{Ca}_2\text{FeSi}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlSi}_2\text{O}_7$, nepheline rich in NaAlSiO_4 and $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$, Feldspar rich in $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$ and the pure compounds $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$ and CaTiO_3 . Some unreduced iron seems to be present in the melilite phase, which is contradicting the experimental results, however, its amount is low and as such might not form experimentally. CaTiO_3 and nepheline are well predicted. At the higher temperature the predicted solution phases are Fe-FCC which indicates phase transition, nepheline rich in NaAlSiO_4 and $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$, melilite rich in and $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_3\text{O}_7$, $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlSi}_2\text{O}_7$ and less $\text{Ca}_2\text{FeSi}_2\text{O}_7$. However, still the amount of melilite is low and as such it might be challenging to observe it experimentally. Feldspar is also predicted and at this temperature is composed of $\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$. The pure compounds $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$ and CaTiO_3 are also predicted. In general, increasing the temperature, reduces the melilite upon further iron reduction whereas feldspar ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$) solid solution increases in amount upon more CaO availability (from the melilite phase). Nepheline and $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$ are the dominant phases.

Iron reduction occurs almost completely from the low temperature regime and the path for iron reduction seems to go through the formation and subsequent reduction of the spinel and the iron present in melilite solid solutions. Other phases are not seen experimentally which might still be attributed to kinetic effects in addition to deviations during the experiments in comparison to the thermodynamic simulations.

It can be claimed that there is a fair agreement with the experimental results regarding the conditions for iron reduction and the formation of the main phases in the bulk. However, at the high temperature gehlenite was observed experimentally whereas in the simulations the dominant phases are nepheline and $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$. It seems that thermodynamically phases containing Na are predominant whereas experimentally that was not the case expect of the low temperature regime. This contradiction might be attributed to several reasons such as variations in the composition of BR, thermodynamic overestimation of Na phases in the system. Further work is required to justify the exact reasons, however, still the simulations can give valuable insight into the reduction path and the dominant phases present. Considering the expected deviations in the composition of BR that can result in apparent deviations in the phase assembly and the differences in the actual processing and theoretical approximations on the materials characteristics, the bulk phases are in a fair agreement between the simulations and the experiments. From the previous experimental work it has been found that there is sodium loss during the hydrogen reduction¹⁶.

Considering 10 wt.% CaCO_3 additions the phase assembly deviates regarding the formation of dominant phases (Figure A6 in appendix). At the low temperature regime, melilite rich in $\text{Ca}_2\text{FeSi}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Ca}_2\text{AlSi}_2\text{O}_7$, nepheline rich in NaAlSiO_4 , $\text{Na}_2\text{CaAl}_4\text{O}_8$ and the pure compounds $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$, CaTiO_3 are the predicted phases. Experimentally, metallic iron is forming as predicted by the simulations, in addition to CaTiO_3 and nepheline solid solution. However, magnetite is the remaining iron phase according to the experiments, whereas in the

simulations, remaining iron oxide is seen in the melilite phase. This is due to the thermodynamic stability of the solution phase which might be hindered due to kinetic effects in the experiments. At the higher temperature regime, metallic iron is the dominant Fe-containing phase in addition to melilite, which is rich in $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_1\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Ca}_2\text{Al}_3\text{O}_7$ and less $\text{Ca}_2\text{FeSi}_2\text{O}_7$ that indicates more iron reduction at higher temperatures. Still, Na-containing phases are overestimated in the thermodynamic simulations, for reasons mentioned above.

Considering 30% CaCO_3 additions, iron is reduced almost completely from the low temperature regime as seen experimentally (Figure A7 in appendix). Some iron is found in the olivine phase but its amount within the solution remains low. Thermodynamically this could be explained upon the reduction of the activity of iron in the system with increasing Ca amount although the atmosphere might have higher partial pressure of O_2 . Metallic iron is the dominant Fe-phase at all the temperatures which agrees between the experiments and the simulations. The more CaO availability in the system changes the phase assembly and more Ca-containing phases are formed in comparison with the previous cases. Olivine solution rich in Ca_2SiO_4 , $\text{Ca}_5\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{13}$, $\text{Na}_2\text{CaAl}_4\text{O}_8$, $\text{Na}_2\text{Ca}_3\text{Al}_{16}\text{O}_{28}$ and $\text{Ca}_5(\text{SiO}_4)_2\text{CO}_3$ are the predicted phases at low temperature. According to the experimental results brownmillerite appears which is a Al-Ca-Fe-O compound. However, thermodynamically this was not predicted. At higher temperatures, CaTi solution, which is rich in $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ti}_2\text{O}_6$, forms instead of the experimentally determined perovskite. In addition, melilite is predicted in agreement with the experiments at the high temperature regime. As mentioned earlier, phases rich in Na are not detected in the experimental results.

The ternary composition has been further used to represent better the influence of the CaO additions on the phase assembly isolating parallel reactions and more complicated computations. It can be seen in the following Figure 11. As shown in Figure 11, increasing

calcium oxide shifts the phase composition from Al_2O_3 , $\text{CaO}\cdot 6\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CaO}\cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, , $\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $12\text{CaO}\cdot 7\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $3\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$, $\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and finally CaO . Among these, $12\text{CaO}\cdot 7\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{CaO}\cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ are the most alkali-leachable phases. Therefore, the primary objective of adding CaO to bauxite residue is to promote the formation of these alumina-containing phases, facilitating alumina extraction through later alkali leaching ⁷⁾. Increasing the amount of CaO by 10 wt.% shifts the system to the primary area of CaAl_4O_7 whereas when CaO is added to 30% the system will be in the melilite area.

Figure 11: Ternary Phase diagram of CaO , Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 system with 1000 °C to 1600 °C temperature projection

The simulations and the experimental results agree regarding the reduction of iron oxides, indicating the thermodynamic feasibility of the reduction in H_2 environment. In addition, the phase assembly is pretty much in a fair agreement as perovskite, melilite, and nepheline seem to predominate. As mentioned, gehlenite is observed experimentally, which is an endmember in the melilite solid solution. In addition, the formation of mayenite is predicted on the simulations but its formation is quite low experimentally. However, it seems that increasing the CaO additions has the tend to drive the system to leachable aluminate phases such as CaAl_2O_7 , CaAl_2O_4 , and $\text{Ca}_{12}\text{Al}_{14}\text{O}_{33}$.

4. Conclusions

Hydrogen reduction of BR and BR-Calcite pellets were carried out and the products were characterized. The results are summarized as below

- The initial rate of reduction of BR and BR-Calcite pellets is similar at 1000 °C, while BR-Calcite pellets have a faster secondary stage of reduction.

- The extent of reduction in initial stage is higher for BR pellet (about 85%) and complete reduction occurs in shorter time compared to BR- Calcite pellets at 1000 °C.
- The formation of $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_5$ phase during heating cycle or prior reduction decreases its reducibility compared to hematite at lower temperatures (below 800°C), while at higher temperatures its reducibility is close to Fe_2O_3 .
- With increasing calcite addition, mayenite phase formation is more favorable compared to gehlenite during hydrogen reduction due to lower free energy of formation and limited SiO_2 present in bauxite residue.
- Thermodynamic simulations provide a powerful tool to do the phases formation prediction and the optimum temperature, composition, and gas conditions for the reduction. In general, the iron reduction process is well predicted considering that kinetic effects are excluded from the simulations.
- The oxide phases that form in the bulk of the sample during sintering deviate with the simulation results, especially for the low CaCO_3 and temperature conditions. Thermodynamics calculation shows the presence of sodium containing calcium aluminate phase, however, in actual experimental work it was not detected possibly because Na is transferred to the gas phase and removed from the actual system. The deviation becomes less at increasing calcite and temperature regimes, which indicates that the results have a higher tendency to thermodynamic equilibrium under the applied conditions.

Future work and Industrial implication:

In future work aimed at optimizing this process, the reduced iron oxide will be separated using physical separation methods. The calcium aluminate formed will be leached with a sodium carbonate solution to recover alumina. Since the reduced pellets contain iron particles which

are small in size, additional heat treatment will be applied to increase their size. Furthermore, as alumina in the reduced pellets remains in the form of gehlenite, which is a non-alkali leachable phase, temperature control particularly the cooling rate will be studied to facilitate the conversion of gehlenite into calcium silicate and alumina phases.

The optimized process has been successfully tested at the pilot scale as part of our HARARE project, achieving effective reduction. However, a key challenge in hydrogen reduction is the presence of unutilized hydrogen. In commercial industrial processes, off-gas recycling is a crucial integrated component for both potential energy savings and economic feasibility. The hydrogen reduction of bauxite residue can only be economically viable if, in addition to iron and alumina recovery, rare earth metals are also separated. Since bauxite residue contains a fraction of scandium, its extraction would enhance the overall economic feasibility of the process.

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Figure 1: Overview of experimental procedure and applied characterization methods

Figure 2: XRD spectra of calcined BR+10cal pellets at different temperatures.

Figure 3: Weight reduction with time for 3 different types of pellets at 1000 °C (a) BR pellets reduction with variation of temperature (b) BR+10cal pellets reduction with variation of temperature (c) BR+30cal pellets with variation with temperature (d).

Figure 4: XRD of reduced BR, BR+10cal and BR+30cal pellets at 1000 °C.

(a) BR Reduced Pellets

(b) BR+30cal Reduced Pellets

(c) BR+30cal Reduced Pellets

Figure 5: SEM images of (a) BR reduced pellets (b) BR+10cal reduced pellets (b) BR+30cal reduced pellets (All pellets reduced at 1000 °C).

Figure 6: Elemental mapping of BR pellets reduced at 1000 °C.

Figure 7: Elemental mapping of BR+30cal reduced 1000 °C pellets

Figure 8:(a) Elemental Mapping of Reduced BR+30% CaCO₃ pellets at 800 °C pellets.

Figure 8:(b) Compositional analysis of different phases in reduced BR+30% CaCO₃ pellets at 800 °C.

Figure 9:(a) Elemental Mapping of the reduced BR pellets at 600 °C.

Element	Wt. %
Al	53.05
O	46.95

Element	Wt. %
Fe	82.39
O	14.03
Ti	03.58

Element	Wt. %
Fe	62.27
O	34.20
Al	03.53

Element	Wt. %
Ti	41.16
O	58.84

Figure 9:(b) Compositional analysis of different phases in the reduced BR pellets at 600 °C.

Figure 10: Thermodynamics calculation of BR pellets at different reduction temperature

Figure 11: Ternary Phase diagram of CaO,Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ system with 1000 °C to 1600 °C temperature projection

Table 1: XRF elemental analysis of BR and calcite

Materials/oxides	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	K ₂ O	MnO	MgO	Na ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	LOI
BR	22	8.8	40.71	0.09	0.08	0.23	3.1	0.11	0.95	7.1	5	12.4
Calcite	0.9	52.7	0.15	0.12	0.95	0.01	0.06	2.07	0.03	42.6

Table 2: Initial rate of reduction (mol/sec) of pellets at different temperatures.

Pellets/Temperature	1000 °C	800 °C	600 °C
BR	0.000921	0.000586	0.000243
BR+10cal	0.000636	0.000417	0.0000859
BR+30cal	0.000611	0.000335	0.0000521

Appendix

Figure A1: Schematic representation of phase formation of BR and BR calcite pellets during heating

Figure A2: Phase analysis of calcined BR and BR+30cal at 1000 °C

Figure A3: XRD spectra of the reduced BR pellets at different temperatures.

Figure A4: XRD spectra of the reduced BR+10cal pellets at different temperatures.

Figure A5: XRD of reduced BR+30cal pellets

Figure A6: Thermodynamices calculation of BR+10cal at different tempertaure

Figure A7: Thermodynamices calculation of BR+30cal pellets at different reduction temperatures.